

DETERMINATION OF ALIPHATIC THIOCARBAMIDES

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The volumetric determination of mono-, di-, tri- and tetra-methylthiocarbamides has been described using iodine and mercuric nitrate.

Several methods have been proposed for the determination of thiocarbamide. These depend on (i) desulphurisation (Volhard, *Ber.*, 1874, 7, 100; Cuthill and Atkins, *J. Soc. Chem. Ind.*, 1937, 56, 5r), (ii) oxidation of thiocarbamidic sulphur to sulphate (Cuthill and Atkins, *loc. cit.*), (iii) formation of the formamidine disulphide by oxidation with iodine (Reynolds, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1903, 83, 1; Werner, *ibid.*, 1912, 101, 2166) and (iv) complex formation with mercuric nitrate (Williams, *J. Soc. Chem. Ind.*, 1939, 58, 77r). To di-, tri and tetra-alkyl substituted thiocarbamides, which are difficultly desulphurised and oxidised (i) and (ii) cannot be satisfactorily applied. The methods (iii) and (iv), which have also the added advantage of being simple titrimetric procedures, were therefore extended to these compounds. The former is a reversible reaction; for its quantitative completion considerable dilution is necessary which varies with the compound (vide Table I). The latter involves the formation of 1 : 1 molecular complex which is stable in aqueous solution and takes precedence in its formation over the reaction of mercuric nitrate with thiocyanate which is used as an indicator.

EXPERIMENTAL

Iodometric Determination.—The compounds were double crystallised from water and their purity confirmed by the melting point and estimation of nitrogen and sulphur. *M/10* solutions were used. The iodine solution was the usual aqueous iodine, *N/10*- in potassium iodide. For every titration different quantities of thiocarbamide solution were taken in a 100 c.c. conical flask and 3 c.c. starch and 2 c.c. dilute sulphuric acid solutions were added and the volume made up to 20 c.c. with water. It was then titrated with iodine as usual. The results with thiocarbamide and its methyl, dimethyl, trimethyl and tetramethyl derivatives are presented in Table I.

TABLE I

<i>M/10</i> thiocarbamide soln.	Conditions				I_2 (<i>N/10</i>) consumed in case of diff. thiocarbamides (in c.c.)						
	H_2SO_4 (dil.)	Starch.	Water.	Total bulk.	Thi.	Me.Thi	Dime. Thi.	Trime. Thi.	Tetrame. Thi.	I_2 (calc.)	
10.00 c.c.	2 c.c.	3 c.c.	5.0 c.c.	20 c.c.	4.20	4.84	2.96	0.98	3.21	10.0 c.c.	
5.00	2	3	10.0	20	2.58	2.96	1.90	0.55	1.87	5.0	
2.50	2	3	12.5	20	1.58	1.74	1.18	0.39	1.17	2.5	
1.25	2	3	13.8	20	0.95	0.99	0.72	0.28	0.72	1.25	
0.62	2	3	14.4	20	0.52	0.54	0.43	0.18	0.43	0.62	
0.30	2	3	14.7	20	0.28	0.28	0.24	0.15	0.24	0.30	
0.20	2	3	14.8	20	0.20	0.20	0.19	0.12	0.14	0.20	
0.10	2	3	14.9	20	0.10	0.10	0.10	0.09	0.10	0.10	

The technique adopted by us of keeping the concentration of the indicator approximately constant by varying only the quantity of thiocarbamide in a fixed bulk of the solution (viz. 20 c.c. in the present case) has the advantage of giving sharp end-points as compared to earlier experiments where dilution was changed by increasing the bulk which must result in a lowering of the indicator : bulk ratio.

Estimation by Mercuric Nitrate.—*M/10* solution (10 c.c.) of the thiocarbamide was taken for every titration. To this were added varying quantities of a standard *N/10* solution of potassium thiocyanate (1 to 20 c.c.) and plain water to change dilution. Mercuric nitrate was prepared of *N/10* concentration from metallic mercury. Ferric alum (prepared as usual in moderately concentrated nitric acid) was used as an indicator, the end-point being indicated by the disappearance of the red colour of ferric thiocyanate. Deduction of the thiocyanate equivalent of mercuric nitrate from the titre value gives the quantity of mercuric nitrate used up by the thiocarbamide. The results are presented in Table II.

TABLE II

<i>M/10</i> thiocarbamide soln.	Conditions				Total bulk.	$\text{Hg}(\text{NO}_3)_2$ equiv. of KCNS (<i>N/10</i>)	Volume of <i>N/10</i> mercuric nitrate solution equivalent to thiocarbamides (corrected for the thiocyanate added in c.c.)				
	KCNS soln. (<i>N/10</i>)	Ferric alum.	Water.	10 c.c.			Thi.	Me.Thi	Dime Thi.	Trime. Thi.	Tetrame. Thi.
10 c.c.	1 c.c.	2 c.c.	0 c.c.	13 c.c.	1	9.95	9.95	9.90	9.90	9.95	
10	1	2	37	50	1	10.0	10.0	10.0	10.0	10.0	
10	1	2	87	100	1	10.0	10.0	10.0	10.0	10.0	
10	10	2	0	22	10	10.0	10.0	10.0	10.0	10.0	
10	10	2	28	50	10	10.0	10.0	10.0	10.0	10.0	
10	10	2	78	100	10	10.0	10.0	10.0	10.0	10.0	
10	20	2	0	32	20	10.0	10.0	10.0	10.0	10.0	
10	20	2	18	50	20	10.0	10.0	10.0	10.0	10.0	
10	20	2	68	100	20	10.0	10.0	10.0	10.0	10.0	

Symbols : Thi. denotes Thiocarbamide
 Me. Thi. " Methylthiocarbamide
 Dime. Thi. " NN-dimethylthiocarbamide
 Trime. Thi. " Trimethylthiocarbamide
 Tetrame. Thi. " Tetramethylthiocarbamide.

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